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INTROSPECTION INTO PORTUGUESE UNIVERSITIES ATTRACTIVENESS : A FOCUS ON INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM), combining management techniques with engineering background, was introduced in Portuguese universities at the beginning of '90. Currently, it occupies a high position in terms of students' preferences, when choosing their university. The main purpose of this paper is to investigate what are the factors influencing IEM students' choice of their universities in Portugal.

A quantitative survey was conducted (n=304) with the participation of ESTIEM (European Students of Industrial Engineering and Management), at Bachelor's and Master's levels, from five Portuguese universities (Porto, Minho, Aveiro, Coimbra and Lisbon). We carried out preliminary statistical analysis of the data.

The findings show that, when choosing a university to study at, the most important factor for students is the prestige of the institution. There are also other relevant factors, such as the city of the university, the companies' recognition and the employability rate. IEM students seem to be future oriented, as they give the highest importance to the job opportunities offered after graduation. However, they associate lower relevance on everyday factors of their academic experience, such as the evaluation methods, the support given by professors and the teaching methodologies utilized.

Findings from this study allow universities to have a better understanding about the most valued factors in the students' decision-making process for choosing their

university, as well as to adapt their recruitment strategy to this demand to attract good students for their programmes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM), combining management techniques with an engineering background, had an important evolution during the past three decades in Portuguese universities.

Nowadays, engineering degrees, and particularly IEM, have seen a rise in interest of Portuguese students. In the past three years, engineering degrees have occupied the podium positions, with the IEM degree of University of Porto always featuring in one of the first four places. In fact, in the academic year 2020/2021, only four out of ten of the top degrees were not from engineering, with IEM in University of Porto being the highest entrance grade with a requirement of 19.13 points out of 20.

IEM is also characterized as a degree with a particularly high employability in Portugal, as can be seen by the unemployment rates stated in Table 1, with data from 2019¹. These low unemployment rates are coherent with the fact that IEM allows students to follow a plethora of career paths in diverse domains (such as quality management, production management, logistics, information systems, process modeling, management control, strategy and marketing, among others).

Furthermore, it is also relevant to mention the numerus clausus, whose data for 2020 for the Bachelor's, Master's and Integrated Master's² is also summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Numerus clausus and unemployment rates for the IEM degrees in Portugal³

University	Aveiro	Coimbra		Lisbon		Minho	Porto
Type of IEM Degree	Integrated Master's	Bachelor's	Master's	Bachelor's	Master's	Integrated Master's	Integrated Master's
Numerus Clausus	74	54	45	69	30	59	93
Unemployment rate	2.3%	2.6%	3.9%	0.7%	0.4%	6.1%	2%

Considering the overall scenario of IEM in Portugal, it becomes very interesting to investigate the factors that lead students to their choice of university to pursue an IEM degree, as it can provide valuable insights to Portuguese universities. Their gain in terms of a better understanding of the most influential factors for the decision making of students can translate into direct actions towards them. University management can adapt both their marketing and recruitment strategies according to these factors, with the aim of attracting the best talent for their institutions.

In order to understand the influencing factors for student's first choice of university and their perception of their current university's attractiveness, a quantitative study was designed and conducted by students of ESTIEM (European Students of

¹ The unemployment rates utilized are from 2019, in order to avoid possible fluctuations due to the influence of the Covid-19 pandemic, so that conclusions could be made on the employability scenario of a regular year. These rates correspond to the amount of unemployed that graduated between 2015 and 2019, per total amount of graduates for those years. More information on the website: <https://www.dgeec.mec.pt/np4/92/>

² An Integrated Masters is a combination of Bachelor's and Master's degree in a continuous course.

³ Data from the Direção-Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência (DGEEC) - General Center for Statistics of Education and Science.

Industrial Engineering and Management), a non-profit organization that connects students of IEM European-wide and has a strong representation inside Portuguese universities.

This study especially relevant in the Portuguese context, since it is the first to investigate the question of attractiveness in Portuguese universities, particularly in IEM degrees.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

With the transformation of higher education to a highly competitive and globalized environment, there is a growing interest in research about students' choice of their universities. According to the conceptual model of Perna et al. [1], students' choice are influenced by the following four attributes: (1) habitus (demographic characteristics, social and cultural capital), (2) school and community context (availability of resources, type of resources, structural supports and barriers), (3) higher education context (institutional characteristics, location, marketing and recruitment) and (4) social, economic and social context. As highlighted by Han [2], students' university choice is a complex decision-making process based on the combination of numerous factors in interaction (for example the students' habitus and institutional characteristics).

For Maringe [3], there is a strong influence of future employment and career prospects in students' decision by applying a consumerist benefice-value approach considering their enrollment as a long-term investment. As highlighted by Conard and Conard [4], students give main importance to the academic reputation in their university choice process: they choose more likely an institution with a very good reputation in view of increasing their employability perspectives. In a recent work, Moulignier et al. [5] underlined the influence of diverse factors on French engineering students' preferences like institutional prestige, wide range of specialisation in engineering, extracurricular activities and excellent employability perspectives with access to high ranked job opportunities.

The work of Briggs [6], investigating students' choices in Scotland, identified three principal influence factors: academic reputation, distance from students' home and location. On the opposite side, the two least influential factors for students in this area were the information supplied by the university and its research reputation. The high influence of geographical factors was confirmed by Gibbons and Vignoles [7] who provided evidence that the distance between institution and students' home has a very high influence on students' decision (more particularly for students who have to stay at home for financial or cultural reasons). According to Sá et al. [8], Portuguese students' decision to leave their hometown related not only to the accessibility of University but also they have preferences over leisure activities.

3 METHODOLOGY

To answer the research question, an online quantitative study was designed in order to investigate what are the most influential factors for IEM students on their decision making process for choosing their university.

This study was designed and shared through five different Portuguese universities with an IEM degree - Universities of Aveiro, Coimbra, Lisbon, Minho and Porto. These are highly relevant universities in the Portuguese context and correspond to the ones in Portugal that have a student's organization associated with ESTIEM.

The respondents of the survey are all engineering students in the Industrial Engineering and Management degree of these universities, both from the Bachelor's and Master's degrees. The majority of the respondents (83%), were at the Bachelor level, with 22% of the respondents being in their first year. The data is well distributed between the five universities, with participation rates between 15.13%, and 26.6% as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Percentage of respondents per university and study level

University	Aveiro		Coimbra		Lisbon		Minho		Porto	
% of respondents (BSc and MSc)	93%	7%	77%	23%	100%	0%	85%	15%	72%	28%
% of respondents (total)	15%		27%		17%		19%		22%	

The distribution between female and male respondents is 60% and 40%. The data was collected during a month (March 2021), through the local representatives of the student organizations, and handled anonymously.

The survey was divided in two main sections: one relative to students' first choice of university when applying for it and the other relative to their current university and what they consider attractive about it. For this study, four questions were considered. Relative to the first section, students were questioned about their first choice of university, having the chance to choose two other universities besides the ones analysed in this study, as well as to write other options, to make sure all possibilities were considered. Besides, they were also questioned about the influence of external factors on their choice. In this part, we used a five points Likert scale for the answers. Finally, in both sections of the survey there were closed multiple selection questions: respondents were asked to select a maximum of six factors out of fifteen that led them to their first choice of university, and a maximum of three factors out of six that make their current university degree attractive.

The principal limitation of the study is the fact that only engineering students of IEM from five Portuguese universities were surveyed. Although, when asked about their first choices, students still had the option to point out universities outside of the five universities chosen as the scope of this research. For several practical reasons, we decided to exclude these answers from our data analysis. Besides, it is also important to consider the limitations associated with the method utilized (self-reported opinion survey) and the fact that students were asked about a choice they made in previous years.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Oftentimes students have a certain university as their first choice, which does not necessarily correspond to the one they end up studying in. As so, it is important to analyze both the factors that lead to their first choice and the ones they consider to make their current university attractive.

4.1 Influencing factors for student’s first choice of university

In order to study the influence of external factors that lead students to choose where to study, students were questioned about whether parents, friends, media and high school professors played a relevant role on their decision making. Our results, presented in Table 3, indicate that the respondents didn’t consider either of them as influential on their university choice.

Table 3. External influences on student’s first choice of university

	Totally disagree (1)		Disagree (2)		Neither agree or disagree (3)		Agree (4)		Totally agree (5)		Arithmetic average (̄)		Standard deviation (±)	
	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	̄	±		
Influenced by Parents	67x	22.95	74x	25.34	69x	23.63	67x	22.95	15x	5.14	2.62	1.21		
Influenced by Friends	83x	28.42	92x	31.51	72x	24.66	39x	13.36	6x	2.05	2.29	1.08		
Influenced by the Media	44x	15.07	68x	23.29	56x	19.18	101x	34.59	23x	7.88	2.97	1.23		
Influenced by High School Professors	85x	29.11	87x	29.79	67x	22.95	44x	15.07	9x	3.08	2.33	1.14		

Regarding the factors related to the universities themselves, Figure 1 shows the overall results, where the prestige of the university is pointed as the most influential.

Fig. 1. Students’ influencing factors for choosing their university

When analysing the results, the prestige of the institution is a major factor in all universities, which is in line with the study of Conard and Conard [4], pinpointing reputation as highly relevant.

The city of the university also affirms itself as a very relevant factor, especially in Coimbra, which can be justified by the fact that it is a renowned student city with a great academic spirit and traditions. Besides the actual location, it is important to consider that students oftentimes need to go out of their city to study, so hometown proximity was also a reviewed factor, particularly relevant to the students of Minho

an Coimbra. This high relevance of distance from students' home and location of the university confirm also the results of Briggs [6] and Gibbons and Vignoles [7].

Looking in a more corporate perspective, recognition by companies and employability rate also affirm themselves as relevant factors. The first plays an important role especially in Lisbon and Porto, but the employability rate has a transversal relevance across all universities, with the exception of Coimbra, which is in line with the high employability rates for all IEM degrees in Portugal, seen before in Table 1.

However, not all results are similar across universities. For example, only students that have chosen Aveiro highlighted infrastructures as an influencing factor in their choice, and only the ones who chose Lisbon highlighted international recognition of the university as relevant, possibly due its location in the capital of the country and having more professors involved in collaborations at international level.

Overall, the least relevant factors of students' choice are the easiness/difficulty of the university, insufficiency of marks for attending a preferred one, the companies it has associated as partners and the teaching methodologies of the degree.

The percentages of choices per factor for each university, as well as the total percentage, are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Students' first choice attractiveness factors per university

First Choice Factor	University					Mean	SD
	Aveiro	Coimbra	Lisbon	Minho	Porto		
Prestige	15%	20%	17%	15%	17%	17%	2%
City	13%	25%	11%	14%	14%	15%	5%
Recognition by Companies	8%	4%	17%	12%	15%	11%	5%
Employability Rate	12%	5%	13%	12%	15%	11%	4%
Scientific Reputation	10%	6%	11%	6%	10%	9%	3%
Hometown Proximity	5%	13%	5%	15%	7%	9%	5%
International Recognition	2%	5%	11%	3%	4%	5%	4%
Extracurricular Opportunities	10%	8%	0%	8%	3%	6%	4%
Infrastructures	10%	3%	2%	4%	2%	4%	3%
Curriculum	4%	5%	3%	2%	4%	4%	1%
Teaching Methodologies	6%	1%	1%	6%	2%	3%	3%
Difficulty	0%	1%	5%	1%	3%	2%	2%
Company Partners	3%	2%	1%	4%	2%	2%	1%
Insufficient Marks for Preferred University	1%	4%	0%	0%	0%	1%	1%
Easiness	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Finally, the data of this study indicated that for numerous students there is a mismatch between the university they put as first choice and the one they are currently enrolled in. From the 255 students that stated their first choice, 56 were enrolled in a different one. There is a clear preference for University of Porto, being the first choice of 35% of the students, and corresponding to the preferred option of 33 out of the 56 mismatches between first choice and current university.

4.2 Attractiveness perception of the currently enrolled university

When questioned about what attracts them the most in their current degree, IEM students showed a notable preference in the job opportunities offered by the degree, as 40% of the respondents chose this factor as the most attractive. As indicated in

Table 5, this choice was identical among all Portuguese universities, with students from Porto and Lisbon distinguishingly preferring this factor over others. This is in line with the fact that Lisbon and Porto are the first and second biggest cities in Portugal, where the majority of the big companies are located, therefore having more job opportunities. Overall, this comes to show once again the bigger importance given to the opportunities that come after the degree, rather than the degree itself.

Table 5. Attractiveness of the current degree par university

Curent Degree Factor	University					Mean	SD
	Aveiro	Coimbra	Lisbon	Minho	Porto		
Job Market Opportunities	37%	38%	47%	31%	46%	40%	7%
Content Taached	19%	23%	26%	18%	24%	22%	3%
Companies Involvement in Subjects	17%	7%	16%	23%	12%	15%	6%
Professors' Support	13%	18%	9%	10%	10%	12%	3%
Teaching Methodologies	11%	10%	1%	13%	5%	8%	5%
Evaluation Methods	3%	4%	0%	4%	3%	3%	2%

Following job opportunities, the content of the courses and the involvement of companies in the subjects are the next two most chosen options, rating the importance given to the experience of the course as only slightly relevant. However, in the University of Minho, known for promoting the involvement of companies in their courses, students indicated that this was a quite attractive factor.

Professors' support, evaluation methods and teaching methodologies are the least influencing factors, which again validate the idea that, in a general way, Portuguese IEM students are not really attracted by the actual experience of the course. Nevertheless, it isn't clear whether this is because their degree isn't a very pleasant experience to them or because this is simply not as relevant as their future careers.

5 CONCLUSION

In summary, this paper presents an analysis on the factors that influence IEM students' choice of university and perceived attractiveness of the one they are enrolled in. According to our findings, the most influential factor is the prestige of the University followed by the city of the institutions. Recognition by companies and employability rate are also very relevant, and in line with the context of IEM in Portugal. Concerning the attractiveness of their current university, there is an overall high relevance on the job market opportunities that students expect to access after their graduation.

The present findings provide a better understanding of students' values and motivations to choose their engineering degree as well as their appreciation of the current degree. These insights could give useful indication for universities to adapt of their recruitment and marketing strategies, and eventually even the strategic development of their IEM degree. As an example, it could be a valuable opportunity to develop a more active involvement of companies in the degree to improve their general recognition or reinforce the university reputation and image with specific and targeted marketing promotions

Further studies should enlarge the scope of this research, by understanding the attractiveness factors for Portuguese students of other engineering degrees, or by comparing the results for the IEM students in these Portuguese universities with others studying IEM in universities in other countries, in order to provide a larger European or international vision.

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